

Supplementary Material

Drago, A., Green, T.M.J., and Bailey, N.W.B. Genotype and social environment influence female-female interactions in a non-social insect. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*. DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2025.1007

Table S1. Model expressions for all statistical analyses performed

Dependent Variable	Model expression
Antennal contact occurrence (Binomial GLM)	~ focal genotype * partner genotype * acoustic treatment + focal mass + interacting mass
Biting occurrence (Binomial GLM)	~ focal genotype * partner genotype * acoustic treatment + focal mass + interacting mass
Flight attempt occurrence (Binomial GLM)	~ focal genotype * partner genotype * acoustic treatment + focal mass + interacting mass
Antennal contact frequency (log(x+1) LM)	~ focal genotype * partner genotype * acoustic treatment + focal mass + interacting mass
Biting frequency (Negative Binomial GLM)	~ focal genotype + partner genotype + acoustic treatment + focal mass + interacting mass

Flight attempt frequency (Negative Binomial GLM)	~ focal genotype + partner genotype + acoustic treatment
Antennal contact duration (log(x+1) LM)	~ focal genotype * partner genotype * acoustic treatment + focal mass + interacting mass
Correlation biting occurrence – antennal contact frequency (Kendall Correlation)	<i>biting occurrence, antennal contact frequency,</i> method=c("kendall")
Correlation biting frequency – antennal contact frequency (Kendall Correlation)	<i>biting frequency, antennal contact frequency,</i> method=c("kendall")
Flight attempt frequency (preliminary analysis; log(x+1) LM)	~ focal mass + partner mass

Table S2. Results of ICC analysis for 2 raters, n=20, R threshold of roughly 0.7.

Behaviour	R score of frequency (p value)	R score of duration (p value)
Empty	0.606 (p=0.047)	0.854 (p=3.06e-7)
Receiving mounting	6.94e-17(0.5)*	6.94e-17(p=0.5)*
Mounting	6.94e-17(0.5)*	6.94e-17(p=0.5)*
Movement	0.561(p=0.0501)**	0.939(p=0.00077)**
Antennal contact	0.832(p=0.000103)	0.674(p=0.00103)
Biting	0.87 (p=1.56e-7)	0.925(p=1.08e-8)
Flight attempts	0.8(p=4.37e-6)	0.8(p=4.37e-6)

*mounting and receiving mounting were decided on a basis of consultation between scorers on each case within scoring.

**movement was excluded from the analysis.

Table S3. Results of iteratively run binomial GLMs ($n = 1000$) of all occurrence analyses.

Behaviour	Predictor	Mean X^2 (\pm s.e.)	Df	Iterations in which $p < 0.05$
Antennal	Focal genotype	1.485 (± 0.056)	1	100
	Contact			
	Partner genotype	1.662 (± 0.054)	1	107
	Song	19.620 (± 0.109)	1	1000
	Focal mass	0.514 (± 0.024)	1	6
	Partner mass	0.460 (± 0.021)	1	5
	Focal genotype: Partner genotype	1.998 (± 0.037)	1	79
	Focal genotype: Song	1.680 (± 0.060)	1	116
	Partner genotype: Song	0.884 (± 0.039)	1	37
	Focal genotype: Partner genotype: Song	0.578 (± 0.018)	1	0
Biting	Focal genotype	0.889 (± 0.036)	1	30
	Partner genotype	0.927 (± 0.037)	1	36
	Song	4.509 (± 0.073)	1	561
	Focal mass	0.796 (± 0.035)	1	38
	Partner mass	1.959 (± 0.066)	1	159
	Focal genotype: Partner genotype	0.335 (± 0.017)	1	2
	Focal genotype: Song	0.577 (± 0.027)	1	13
	Partner genotype: Song	0.799 (± 0.036)	1	26
	Focal genotype: Partner genotype: Song	1.155 (± 0.040)	1	48

Flight Attempt	Focal genotype	0.799 (± 0.038)	1	31
	Partner genotype	1.256 (± 0.053)	1	82
	Song	1.240 (± 0.045)	1	67
	Focal mass	0.735 (± 0.030)	1	10
	Partner mass	1.013 (± 0.042)	1	43
	Focal genotype: Partner genotype	1.246 (± 0.055)	1	79
	Focal genotype: Song	3.063 (± 0.089)	1	321
	Partner genotype: Song	1.132 (± 0.047)	1	69
	Focal genotype: Partner genotype: Song	1.051 (± 0.047)	1	67

Table S4. Results of iteratively run linear models ($n = 1000$) for antennal contact frequency ($\log x + 1$)

Predictor	Mean F-value (\pm s.e.)	Iterations in which $p < 0.05$
Focal Genotype	0.753 (± 0.035)	21
Partner genotype	1.183 (± 0.048)	60
Song	27.403 (± 0.201)	1000 *
Focal mass	0.616 (± 0.027)	10
Partner mass	0.501 (± 0.022)	5
Focal genotype:Partner genotype	2.104 (± 0.046)	105
Focal genotype:Song	1.344 (± 0.052)	78
Partner genotype:Song	4.423 (± 0.11)	467
Focal genotype:Partner genotype:Song	4.069 (± 0.064)	468

*Predictors determined to be biologically significant (see Methods) are indicated in bold

Table S5. Results of iteratively run linear models ($n = 1000$) for antennal contact duration ($\log x + 1$)

Predictor	Mean F-value (\pm s.e.)	Iterations in which $p < 0.05$
Focal genotype	1.473 (± 0.052)	84
Partner genotype	2.001 (± 0.059)	150
Song	10.218 (± 0.101)	990 *
Focal mass	0.562 (± 0.026)	12
Partner mass	0.767 (± 0.034)	19
Focal genotype: Partner genotype	4.624 (± 0.064)	601 *
Focal genotype (<i>Nw</i>): Song	1.412 (± 0.054)	81
Partner genotype: Song	4.349 (± 0.099)	473
Focal genotype: Partner genotype: Song	1.092 (± 0.028)	8

*Predictors determined to be biologically significant (see Methods) are indicated in bold

Table S6. Results of iteratively run models ($n = 1000$) for biting and flight attempt frequency analyses.

Behaviour	Predictor	Mean X^2 (\pm s.e.)	Df	Iterations in which $p < 0.05$
Biting	Focal genotype	0.598 (± 0.026)	1	12
	Partner genotype	0.630 (± 0.026)	1	12
	Song	0.702 (± 0.026)	1	16
	Focal mass	0.661 (± 0.030)	1	15
	Partner mass	1.707 (± 0.062)	1	136
Flight Attempt	Focal genotype	0.900 (± 0.044)	1	31
	Partner genotype	2.261 (± 0.121)	1	183
	Song	2.338 (± 0.116)	1	195